

Stabilities and Selectivities of Alkali and Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes of Tetraethylene Glycol Dimethyl Ether and Glycols in Methanol

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Manuscript received 3 July 1991, revised 1 November 1991, accepted 7 February 1992

Stability constants of alkali and alkaline earth metal complexes with glycols and glymes have been determined in methanol at 25° using conductometric method. The sequence of log *K* values for diethylene glycol is K⁺ > Na⁺ > Li⁺ for diglyme in K⁺ > Li⁺ ≈ Na⁺ for tetraethylene glycol is K⁺ > Li⁺ > Na⁺ for tetraglyme is K⁺ > Na⁺. The log *K* values are higher for Ca²⁺ than Mg²⁺ with all glycols and glymes.

Information on the complexes with noncyclic polyethers is sparse. Further, the majority of such studies were carried out in water and methanol-water mixtures and information in non-aqueous media is quite sparse. We have recently reported the results of the study of alkali metal complexes with various noncyclic ligands in methanol-water¹. We report herein the conductometric study of some alkali and alkaline earth metal cations (Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺) with glycols and glymes in methanol. The effect of counter anion on stability was also determined.

n = 1 Diethylene glycol (DEG)
n = 2 Triethylene glycol (TrEG)
n = 3 Tetraethylene glycol (TEG)

n = 1 Diglyme (DG)
n = 2 Triglyme (TrG)
n = 3 Tetraglyme (TG)

Δ in spite of increase in ligand concentration. In such cases determination of stability constant is not possible.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ALKALI AND ALKALINE EARTH METAL COMPLEXES WITH POLYETHYLENE GLYCOLS IN METHANOL AT 25°

	Li ⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺
TEG					
Pic	3.3	2.3	3.7	2.8	4.0
Dnp	3.3	3.8	3.2	—	3.0
Onp	—	3.3	3.1	—	3.7
TrEG					
Pic	—	3.3	—	—	3.2
Dnp	—	3.0	3.4	—	3.0
Onp	3.3	4.1	4.3	—	3.2
DEG					
Pic	2.7	3.0	3.6	—	3.2
Dnp	3.0	2.7	3.1	—	3.6
Onp	3.1	3.3	2.5	—	3.5
TG					
Pic	—	3.1	3.7	—	3.0
Dnp	—	3.3	3.8	3.1	—
Onp	3.0	—	3.8	2.6	3.6
TrG					
Pic	—	3.1	—	3.1	3.7
Dnp	—	3.0	—	—	—
Onp	2.9	—	3.3	—	3.3
DG					
Pic	3.2	3.1	3.6	2.6	2.8
Dnp	3.1	—	3.8	2.8	—
Onp	—	3.4	3.1	—	2.8

*Error limit in log *K*, ±0.04 unit.

Results and Discussion

The calculated formation constants of the complexes of Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ ions with different glycols and glymes in methanol are presented in Table 1. The selectivity behaviour of different glycols and glymes towards M²⁺ in methanol is shown in Fig. 1. Δ vs [L]_t/[M]_t plots of alkali metal picrates with glymes (Fig. 2) show an increase in Δ with increase in ligand concentration. This indicates that mobility of the alkali metal complexes is less than that of the alkali metal ion. So conductometric determination of stability constants are possible. For some cases Δ vs [L]_t/[M]_t plots show scarcely any change in

Metal complexes in methanol: Several investigations reported that the linear open-chain tetraethylene glycol dimethyl ether, triglyme and its derivatives form 1 : 1 cation-ligand complexes with alkali metal ions in solution. The results also show that glycols and glymes form less stable complexes than cyclic synthetic and naturally occurring ionophores² and cryptands³. Both the ligands form stronger complexes with K⁺ than Na⁺ and the ratio of their log *K* values are 1.57 and 1.19 for tetraethylene glycol and tetraglyme respectively. The higher selectivity of cyclic polyethers towards

alkali metal cations over glymes results in part from the so called macrocyclic effect⁴. On the other hand, tetraglyme with its flexible chain can easily wraps around the small cation and hence selectivity is lost.

In Fig. 1 are shown the stability constants of different alkali metal complexes with glymes and glycols in methanol. In methanol tetraglyme forms the strongest complex with K^+ and all other ligands show higher value of stability constants for K^+ . It is likely that the higher selectivity of K^+ over Na^+ for tetraethylene glycol and the crown ethers⁵ in methanol is due to the stronger solvation of Na^+ compared to K^+ in the solvent⁶.

Fig. 1. The variation in stability constants of the Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ complexes with polyethylene glycols and glymes in methanol at 25° : (\square) DEG, (\circ) TEG, (\triangle) DG and (\otimes) TG.

The stability of alkaline earth metal complexes with various ionophores in methanol shows higher $\log K$ for Ca^{2+} over Mg^{2+} . This may be due to smaller size of the Mg ion. The cation is so strongly solvated that considerably more energy must be expended in the desolvation than for the larger Ca ion.

Anion effect: It is seen that the effect of anion is almost negligible in methanol. The salts may exist in both free and ion-paired states, depending on the nature of the solvent and counter anion. The polar solvent methanol can solvate both cations and anions. So difference in association of various salts would be diminished⁷ which is in accord with the present results.

The above results strongly emphasise the

variability of factors which affect the stability of metal ionophore complexes. Besides chain-length of the open-chain polyethers, the nature of the solvent-cation, solvent-complex and solvent-ligand interactions, the relative donor abilities of heteroatom in the chain as well as flexibility are also of considerable importance.

Experimental

Polyethylene glycols (Fluka) and glymes (Merck) were used as such.

For the preparation of alkali and alkaline earth metal picrates, picric acid and metal carbonate taken in 1:1 and 2:1 ratios were dissolved in alcohol and water separately. They were mixed together with continuous stirring, concentrated and the resulting crystals were dried.

Metal dinitrophenolates and metal orthonitrophenolates were prepared by the same procedures.

Conductometric measurement was made on a Systronics 304 conductivity bridge.

Fig. 2. Δ vs $[L]_t/[M]_t$ plots for alkali metal complexes with tetraglyme in methanol at 25° : (\bullet) Li^+ , (\blacksquare) Na^+ and (\blacktriangle) K^+ .

In the experimental procedure to determine the stability constant, a $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution of metal salt (MPic, MDnp and MOnp) and a $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of the ligand (glycol or glyme) were prepared in methanol. Conductivity of the 200 ml solution of the metal salt was measured. The solution of the ligand was added to the solution of the metal salt in instalments of 4 ml and 24–25 readings were taken. The calculations for obtaining stability constants were same as described in literature⁸.

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